

Environmentally-Adaptive Automated Target Recognition Algorithm Using Parametric Characterization of Seabed Textures

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Abstract—The undersea survey mission performed with a side scan sonar system can generate large volumes of data. Automating the detection and classification process using automated target recognition (ATR) is desirable to reduce post processing times and manning requirements. Traditionally ATR algorithms are trained using image exemplars representing the intended target, false targets and the expected operating environment. However, given the variability of the undersea environment, training a single ATR on all environments may degrade performance when operating in a specific environment, since operating thresholds are fixed. In this paper, we propose an ATR algorithm that changes its operating thresholds based on seabed texture parameter estimates of the sonar image statistics. A large set of sonar images with targets inserted at various ranges and orientations against various backgrounds was synthesized. The environmentally-adaptive ATR algorithm was trained on these specific environments and the optimal classification thresholds were stored in a look-up table (LUT). Upon encountering a novel test pattern, the environmental parameters of the sonar image texture are estimated and then used to index the LUT for the appropriate ATR operating threshold. Using this methodology, we show a performance increase for an adaptive ATR that encounters variable seabed environments versus an ATR algorithm with fixed operating thresholds trained with sonar images representative of a wide variety of environments.¹

I. INTRODUCTION

The undersea survey mission performed with a side scan sonar system can generate large volumes of data. When searching for specific undersea targets the sonar data is reviewed by an operator. Fast, accurate automatic target recognition (ATR) algorithms reduce post processing times

and reduce manning requirements. Traditionally ATR algorithms are trained using image exemplars representing the intended target, false targets and the expected operating environment. However, given the variability of the undersea environment, a classifier non-selectively trained on target exemplars from disparate environments may have degraded performance in a specific environment. For example, an increase in sea floor roughness can enhance scatter intensity drowning out highlights from targets; and periodic topographic features, such as sand ripples or patches of high and low intensity can mask target shadow or highlight features. Manifestations of the changing environment in the sonar image such as these degrade the ATR's accuracy in benign environments and increase the number of false positives or false alarms in difficult environments.

In an effort to improve ATR operating performance across a wide spectrum of environments, we propose an ATR algorithm that changes its operating thresholds based on seabed texture parameter estimates from each sonar image. A texture model based on the autocorrelation function (ACF) of the sonar intensity image is used to generate synthetic image textures with known environmental statistical parameters. Synthetic targets are inserted into the textured images at various ranges and orientations. The environmentally-adaptive ATR algorithm is trained on these specific environments and the optimal classification thresholds are stored in a look-up table (LUT). Upon encountering a novel test pattern, the environmental parameters of the background sonar image texture are estimated using the same ACF model and then used to index the LUT for the appropriate ATR operating threshold. Using this methodology, we expect a performance increase for an adaptive ATR that encounters variable seabed environments versus an ATR algorithm with fixed operating

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thresholds trained with sonar images representative of all known environments.

A data set of over 66,000 simulated sonar images was generated for the analysis presented in this paper. This set includes five targets simulated at various ranges and orientations inserted into 30 different seabed textures. The thresholds for classifiers trained in each of these environments were determined and cataloged by texture parameter in a LUT for the adaptive classifier. Several classification events were evaluated. A simple K Nearest Neighbor (KNN) classifier was used to evaluate each case. The classification task is to correctly label the objects embedded in the synthetic textured backgrounds as being of the target or non-target class.

The performance of this preliminary approach to an adaptive classifier was evaluated using two metrics; maximum acceptable false alarm rate (FAR) and minimum acceptable probability of classification (Pc). These performance metrics were compared to the baseline case of a non-adaptive ATR algorithm trained on data from pooled environments. The results indicate an increase in performance for the environmentally-adaptive ATR over the non-adaptive ATR.

Section II provides an overview of the methods used to simulate the images for the experiments. There is a description of the texture model that was used to generate the 30 different seabed textures and a summary of the parameter estimation procedure. An explanation of the types of targets simulated is also provided. In Section III the simulated data set and the KNN classifier used for the experiment are described in detail. A description of the experiments is given in Section IV and conclusions are provided in Section V.

II. SYNTHETIC IMAGE GENERATION AND PARAMETER ESTIMATION

Synthetic sonar images with various single-point and two-dimensional correlation parameters were generated using the procedures outlined in [1], [2], [3], [4]. The sonar image pixel model in this paper assumes the K -distributed sonar image pixel intensity $I(x,y)$ is the result of the product of an exponential distribution, representing the noise-like speckle present in sonar images, and a gamma distribution that represents the variation in the seabed texture (also called the sonar cross section) [4]. Correlation is introduced into the model by a correlated gamma random variable that is synthesized by the procedure outlined in [1], [2], and [4]. Assuming an ideal imaging point spread function (delta-function), the resulting synthesized image has the parameterized autocorrelation function (ACF) [3], [6]

$$r_I(X,Y) = \mu_I \left(1 + \left(1 + \frac{1}{\nu+1} \right) \delta(X,Y) + \frac{1}{\nu+1} e^{-\frac{X^2}{2l_x^2} - \frac{Y^2}{2l_y^2}} \right), \quad (1)$$

where μ_I and ν are the mean and the shape parameter of the single-point pixel intensity statistics, l_x is the spatial correlation length in the X -lag direction and l_y is the spatial

correlation length in the Y -lag direction. The next two subsections outline the procedures to generate synthetic images with specified ACF and single-point statistical parameters and also to estimate these parameters from the synthesized imagery.

A. Textured Image Synthesis Procedure

The following steps will generate a K -distributed N -by- N synthetic sonar intensity image $I(x,y)$ with mean μ_I , shape parameter ν , and an ACF defined in (1).

1. Create an N -by- N zero-mean unit variance white Gaussian noise image $G(x,y)$.
2. Create the desired Gaussian N -by- N ACF $r_G(X,Y)$ by mapping the gamma correlation coefficients from

$$\rho(X,Y) = e^{-\frac{X^2}{2l_x^2} - \frac{Y^2}{2l_y^2}}, \quad (2)$$

into Gaussian correlation coefficients via the procedure described in [4].

3. Filter $G(x,y)$ with the spectrum of $r_G(X,Y)$.
4. Assign pixel values to the correlated gamma random variable image $\Gamma(x,y)$ via the operation [4], [5], [6]

$$\Gamma(x,y) \leftarrow F_G^{-1} \left(F_G(G(x,y)) \middle| \nu+1, \frac{1}{\sqrt{\nu+1}} \right), \quad (3)$$

where $F_G^{-1} \left(P(x) \middle| \nu+1, \frac{1}{\sqrt{\nu+1}} \right)$ is the inverse cumulative gamma distribution function with shape parameter $\nu+1$ and scale parameter $\sqrt{\nu+1}^{-1}$ and $F_G(x)$ is the zero-mean unit variance cumulative Gaussian distribution evaluated at the value x .

5. Create an N -by- N unit-mean exponential noise image $E(x,y)$.
6. Create the correlated K -distributed N -by- N sonar image pixel intensity image $I(x,y)$ with mean μ_I by the operation

$$I(x,y) = \Gamma(x,y) \cdot E(x,y) \cdot \frac{\mu_I}{\sqrt{\nu+1}}, \quad (4)$$

where \cdot is an element-wise array multiplication.

B. Parameter Estimation

Given an unknown texture with a parameterized ACF given by (1), the parameter set $\Theta = \{\nu, l_x, l_y\}$ is found by maximum likelihood estimation [6]. The objective function

$$F(\Theta) = \sum_X \sum_Y \hat{r}_I(X,Y), \quad (5)$$

Is maximized with respect to Θ via the Expectation-Maximization (EM) algorithm for truncated data, where $\hat{r}_I(X, Y)$ is the ACF estimate of intensity image $I(x, y)$ found by

$$\hat{r}_I(X, Y) = IFFT(FFT(I(x, y)) \times (FFT(I(x, y))^*)). \quad (6)$$

A detailed explanation of the parameter estimation technique is contained in [6].

C. Simulated Targets

Fig. 1 depicts the sensing geometry used to generate the simulated targets. Typically a side scan or synthetic aperture sonar system is mounted on an underwater platform such that the main response axis of the sonar imaging beam is illuminating the seafloor. During sonar operation the platform maintains straight and level flight. The transmitter and receiver are co-located. A signal is transmitted and the time-delayed return is recorded. The returned ping is the backscattered energy from the seafloor or objects on the seafloor. These returned pings form a horizontal strip of the final sonar image as indicated in Fig.1. A sonar image of an underwater target proud on the seafloor will typically have a bright region or highlight due to scattering off of the target surface followed by a dark region or shadow cast on the seafloor by the target.

Figure 1. An illustration of the sensing geometry of side-look sonar imaging of underwater targets. In the side-view, top figure, the sensor is displaced off the bottom some distance and ensonifies bottom targets. The top-view, bottom figure shows how each horizontal pixel line is created in the sonar image. The target and shadow regions are labeled in each sonar view [10].

The technique described in [7] was used to generate a set of simulated high resolution sonar snippets of targets sitting proud on the seafloor. There were five different shapes

generated. Examples of each are shown in Fig. 2. The set contains a block, a truncated conical shape, a hollow tube, a solid cylinder, and a tire-shaped object. Each was simulated at various ranges and rotations. The target of interest in this analysis is the truncated cone, Fig. 2(b), which has an approximate cross sectional size of 30 pixels. The other shapes are considered as non-targets for this analysis. In the data set there are also images of an empty seabed, an example of which is shown in Fig. 2(f). The seabed textures for these snippets were generated using the model described in Section II-A. Targets were then embedded in the textured images by segmenting the target and shadow regions from each of the original simulated images. The single-point statistical parameters μ_I and ν are set to 1 and -0.5 respectively, and the texture parameters, l_x and l_y vary and between 3 and 90, depending on the target.

Figure 2. Examples of each of the different target types on various backgrounds. (a) block $l_x=60$ $l_y=15$, (b) truncated cone $l_x=30$ $l_y=3$, (c) Pipe $l_x=90$ $l_y=3$, (d) solid cylinder $l_x=15$ $l_y=90$, (e) tire $l_x=3$ $l_y=3$, (f) no target, $l_x=30$ $l_y=90$.

III. SIMULATED DATA SET

A. Simulated Images

For the analysis, using the method outlined in Section II-A, a set of over 66,000 images was generated. These data consist of 30 different background textures, five different object types as well as images of just the seabed, as in Fig. 2(f).

Table 1 lists the parameters used in the generation of the data set. As in the sample images in Fig. 2, the parameters μ_I and ν were held constant at 1 and -0.5 respectively for the entire set of data. The value of ν was chosen based on the conclusion from [10]. The variation in the optimized parameters was greater for the more difficult environment, $\nu = -0.5$ than for the more benign environment. This implies that there would more of a need for a specifically trained classifier in the more difficult environments. The correlation lengths in the x - and y -directions were chosen to be a function of the diameter of the target of interest, in pixels. For this experiment the truncated cone is the desired target and the diameter is estimated to be 30 pixels. A total of 66790 exemplars were created for the analysis. There were five different correlation lengths simulated in the y -direction and six in the x -direction, as listed in Table I. For each l_x - l_y pair 2224 images of simulated targets were generated, Table II. Out of these, 108 were images of the target, a truncated cone. 200 were images of seabed with no target. The rest were images of non-targets; a pipe, solid cylinder, block and tire. Using the process described in Section II-C, each of these targets were extracted from the original background and inserted into each of the newly generated background textures.

TABLE I
PARAMETERS FOR BACKGROUND TEXTURE

Shape Parameter	ν	-0.5 (moderately difficult environment)
Mean	μ_I	1.0
Spatial Correlation Length y-lag direction	L_y (5)	[0.1 0.5 1 2 3] *TD* pixels
Spatial Correlation Length y-lag direction	L_x (6)	[0.1 0.5 1.5 2 3] *TD* pixels

*Target Diameter

TABLE II
NUMBER OF SIMULATED TARGETS

108	Target (Truncated Cone)
200	No Target
1906	Non- Targets (Pipe, Block, Solid Cylinder, & Tire)
2224	Total Number of Exemplars

B. Classifier

The following provides a brief overview of the K Nearest Neighbor (KNN) classifier chosen for the analysis and is a summary of the development provided in [8, Ch. 2, pp. 124-127]. This simple nonparametric classifier bases the classification decision on the most frequently occurring class in the neighborhood of the test object to be classified.

It is assumed that the observations are independent and identically distributed. Additionally, it is assumed that the observations are drawn from an unknown distribution, $p(x)$. If we consider a small region R, the probability that k of these observations occur within this region is given by the Binomial distribution. Further assuming that the region R is sufficiently small and that the probability density is constant over the region, the probability density function, $p(x)$, can be estimated by,

$$p(x) = \frac{K}{NV(x)}, \quad (7)$$

Where N is the total number of samples and V is the volume holding K samples surrounding the point x to be classified. This technique is called K Nearest Neighbor density estimation. To extend this to the classification problem, the K Nearest Neighbor density estimation technique is applied to each class separately. If we have a data set made up of N_k points in class C_k with N points total, the density associated with each class is given by,

$$p(x|C_k) = \frac{K_k}{N_k V(x)}. \quad (8)$$

The unconditional density is given by (7). The class priors are given by,

$$p(C_k) = \frac{N_k}{N}. \quad (9)$$

Using Bayes' theorem, the posterior probability of class membership is given by,

$$p(C_k|x) = \frac{p(x|C_k)p(C_k)}{p(x)} = \frac{K_k}{K}. \quad (10)$$

The test point x is assigned the classification associated with the highest posterior probability. That is, of the K nearest data points, the class with the greatest representation determines the classification of the test point x . If $K = 1$, then it is called the Nearest Neighbor rule.

The 'training' of the classifier is actually the determination of the multi-dimensional feature vector for a data set whose classifications are known. This feature vector is used to determine the classifications of the test samples. The test sample set is represented by the associated feature vector in

the multidimensional feature space. The Euclidean distance from each element in the test feature vector to each of the training feature vector elements is calculated. Using the K closest neighbors the classification is determined according to (10) for each element in the test sample set. The drawback of this type of classifier is that the class with more frequent occurrences tends to dominate the classification of the test sample set. Additionally, the entire training set must be retained and distances recalculated for each classification determination. Various methods have been developed to address these issues. Assigning weights inversely proportional to the distance to the k points can give more importance to those points that are closer to the test point. To reduce the computational load, techniques such as computing partial distances, prestructuring and editing or pruning the stored prototypes have been developed. For further information the interested reader is directed to [9].

For this analysis, a score is developed for each test sample based on the posterior probability given in (10). Using the definition for total probability and assuming equal prior probabilities of an object of the target or non target class occurring, $p(C_t) = p(C_m) = 1/2$, the calculation for the score is developed below in (11).

$$\begin{aligned} Score_x &= p(C_t|x) = \frac{p(x|C_t)p(C_t)}{p(x)} \\ &= \frac{p(x|C_t)p(C_t)}{p(x|C_t)p(C_t) + p(x|C_m)p(C_m)} \quad (11) \\ &= \frac{p(x|C_t)}{p(x|C_t) + p(x|C_m)} \end{aligned}$$

The score is then compared to a threshold to generate the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curves. The advantage of the KNN classifier is that it is relatively easy to implement and it is strongly consistent. As the number of samples approaches infinity the error rate for the KNN classifier becomes equal to the optimal Bayes rate [9]. The number of points, K , has been chosen to be \sqrt{N} , where N is the total number of samples in the learned data set.

A multi-dimensional feature vector F is calculated from the entire data set for a specific environment. Each feature is listed in Table III. Feature f_1 is calculated from the target highlight pixels, f_2 is calculated from the target shadow pixels and f_3 is calculated from the matched filter pixels. The Matlab® function *regionprops* is then used to calculate 12 additional features, listed as f_4 through f_{15} , for each of these three features. The result is a total of 39 features calculated for each image sample.

To compute f_3 , a range-dependent matched filter is applied to each image. This matched filter is designed to produce high correlations for appropriately sized target regions followed by shadow regions [10]. Because the direction of insonification,

sonar altitude and expected target size are known, the orientation and approximate length of the target shadow can be determined. This knowledge is used to update the matched filter shadow region as the range to the target changes. The feature thresholds η_1 , η_2 , and η_3 were determined using the optimization methods described in [11] and implemented in [10].

The feature set is optimized for each environment using a distance measure,

$$Dist = (T_m - NT_m)^2 / (T_{std} + NT_{std}). \quad (12)$$

The distance measure is the square of the difference between the mean values of the target and non-target features, T_m and NT_m , respectively, divided by the sum of the standard deviations, T_{std} and NT_{std} . Only the three features that provide the greatest discrimination between the target and non-target classes are retained and used in the classifier.

TABLE III
FEATURES

f_1	Highlight Region
f_2	Shadow Region
f_3	Matched Filter Region
f_4	Area
f_5	Major Axis Length
f_6	Minor Axis Length
f_7	Eccentricity
f_8	Orientation
f_9	Convex Area
f_{10}	Filled Area
f_{11}	Euler Number
f_{12}	Equivalent Diameter
f_{13}	Solidity
f_{14}	Extent
f_{15}	Perimeter

IV. EXPERIMENTS

The following section provides a detailed description of each of the two experiments that were conducted as part of this analysis. Table IV provides the parameters for the KNN classifier used for both experiments. T is the number of independent repetitions of the experiment or trials, N is the total number of randomly samples chosen for each iteration of each experiment, K is the number of data points from the feature vector used to classify the test point, and η_1 , η_2 and η_3 , are the feature thresholds for features f_1 , f_2 and f_3 , respectively.

TABLE IV
CLASSIFIER PARAMETERS

T	Number of Trials	20
N	Number of Samples	200
K	K Data Points	$\sqrt{N} \approx 15$
η_1	Number of Highlight Pixels	215
η_2	Number of Shadow Pixels	30
η_3	Number of MF Pixels	600

A. Experiment 1

The goal of the first experiment was to demonstrate the utility of an ATR that is trained for a particular environment. The classifier was trained using data representing the entire range of environments, i.e. the 30 different l_x - l_y combinations. The 200 image exemplars were randomly chosen from this pooled data set and used to train the classifier. The classifier was then tested separately on each of the 30 environments. For each environment an additional set of 200 image exemplars were randomly chosen. All of the results reported are averages over 20 trials.

These results were compared to the results obtained with a classifier trained for a specific environment and subsequently used to classify data from that same specific environment. The same procedure of randomly selecting 200 images exemplars for training and testing and averaging over 20 trails was followed. The results are presented in Figs. 3 and 4.

Figs. 3 and 4 plot the performance of the classifier in terms of the area under the ROC curve (AUC). There is a separate curve for each correlation length in the y direction, l_y . The numbers along the x-axis are each of the x correlation lengths, l_x , represented in the simulated data set. It can be seen that there is an improvement in performance when moving from the generally trained classifier to the specifically trained classifier.

Figure 3. Results of Classifier trained on pooled data and tested on specific data.

Figure 4. Results of Classifier trained on specific data and tested on specific data.

The next experiment demonstrates an implementation of an environmentally adaptable ATR. A look-up table (LUT) was developed that stores the operating thresholds associated with each of the 30 specifically trained classifiers from above, i.e. there is one entry for each l_x - l_y combination.

B. Experiment 2

For the second experiment, the 200 image exemplars were randomly drawn from the entire range of environments. The parameters for the seabed textures were estimated for each of these images using the technique described in Section II-B. These parameters were then used to determine the optimum classifier from the LUT. Each image was classified using its respective estimated classifier. This same set of 200 exemplars was then classified using the classifier for that exact environment. Finally, this same set of data was classified using the classifier that was trained on a pooled set of data from Experiment 1. The results from each of these three

classification events are compared in the following two figures. For the environment specific classifiers, whether the true classifier or classifier chosen from the LUT, the operating thresholds were chosen based on the maximum allowable probability of false alarm, P_{fa} (Fig. 4), and the minimum allowable probability of classification, P_c (Fig. 5).

V. CONCLUSION

A data set of over 66,000 image exemplars with varying background textures and 5 different targets were generated. A description of the parameterized model used to generate the background textures was given along with an outline of the method used to estimate these parameters from simulated images. In the analysis two experiments investigating several different target classification scenarios were conducted. In the first experiment a general classifier trained on a pooled set of data representing a wide range of environments was tested against each environment separately. These results were then compared to the results obtained using a classifier trained for a specific environment and subsequently tested in the same environment. This experiment demonstrates an improvement in classification performance when using a classifier that has been trained for a specific environment.

For the second experiment a LUT of operating thresholds for classifiers optimized for each environment was generated. The image texture parameters were then estimated for each image in a sample set randomly drawn from the pooled set of data. These estimated parameters were used to determine the appropriate classifier from the LUT. The objects in the sample set were then classified using these estimated classifier thresholds and the results are presented. These results are compared to two additional classification events. The first classification event used the general or ‘pooled’ classifier from Experiment 1 and tested it on the pooled sample set of data. In the second event, knowing the actual model parameters used to generate each image in the sample set, the correct classifier is used. The results are promising and indicate that the adaptive ATR provides a performance improvement over the more general classifier, or non-adaptive ATR.

The use of synthetic data may be necessary for training a classifier that will work on real measurements due to cost of collecting a dataset large enough to create robust LUT.

As a follow-on effort the next step will be to perform a sensitivity analysis of classifier thresholds and performance to background texture parameters. There may be regions of environments whose optimized thresholds are essentially the same. This analysis would likely produce a sparse LUT, leading to the development of a functional mapping between texture parameters and optimal classifier thresholds. The advantage will be great savings on storage and classifier training.

It should be noted that the feature thresholds used in the classifier were not optimized for the KNN classifier. They were determined in the analysis presented in [10]. These are optimized for a Kernel Machine type classifier according to the method developed in [11]. However, the feature thresholds were held constant for both experiments. Therefore for this relative performance investigation these thresholds are valid.

Figure 5. ROC curves for the adaptive ATR, specifically trained classifier and the general classifier trained on pooled data. Operating thresholds were chosen based on the maximum acceptable probability of false alarm.

Figure 6. ROC curves for the adaptive ATR, specifically trained classifier and the general classifier trained on pooled data. Operating thresholds were chosen based on the minimum allowable probability of classification.

The results indicate an improvement from the general non-specific classifier to the adaptive classifier, especially at the higher false alarm rates. The specifically trained classifier (Specific-Actual) provides the best performance but it is only slightly better than the adaptive classifier (Specific-Estimated). Error in the parameter estimation will cause a non-optimized classifier to be chosen for a specific environment. This is the probable explanation for the degraded performance of the adaptive classifier.

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